

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF MICROSCOPY WITH ELISA ANTIBODY BASED AMOEBIASIS DIAGNOSIS
IN PATIENTS PRESENTING WITH DYSENTERY AT GOVERNMENT HOSPITALS IN KADUNA
METROPOLIS

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the prevalence and risk factors of *Entamoeba histolytica* infection among dysentery patients presenting at government hospitals in Kaduna metropolis. Three hundred and seventy eight (378) samples were collected, comprising 189 stool and 189 serum specimens. The stool and serum specimens were analysed using Microscopy and Enzyme Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA) respectively. Of the 189 patients sampled, 27 (14.3%) were positive for *Entamoeba histolytica*, 13 (6.9%) *Entamoeba coli* and 4 (2.1%) *Giardia lamblia*. The prevalence of *E. histolytica* infection (14.3%) was higher than the 10% recorded by WHO (1995) in the developing world. Individuals in the age group 1-10 years had the highest prevalence (29.40%) and it decreased with age except for age group 41 years and above. Males were more infected (14.6%) than females (14.0%) but the difference was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). The infection rate was higher in the rainy season (15.5%) than the dry season (12.9%). The study also revealed that *E. histolytica* infection was not statistically associated with educational status and type of toilet facility ($p > 0.05$), but it was however, statistically associated with the occupational status and source of drinking water of the patients ($p < 0.05$).

Key words: *Entamoeba histolytica*, dysentery, Microscopy, Enzyme Linked Immunosorbent Assay

INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that the protozoan *Entamoeba histolytica* is a major cause of morbidity worldwide, causing approximately 50 million cases of dysentery and 100,000 deaths annually (WHO, 1997; Ravdin *et al.*, 2005).

Intestinal amoebiasis due to the infection of *E. histolytica* is ranked third on the list of parasitic protozoan infections leading to death behind malaria and schistosomiasis (Farthing *et al.*, 1996).

Amoebiasis is second only to malaria as a cause of death resulting from a protozoan parasite (WHO, 1997).

Amoebiasis is a rare occurrence in developed countries of the world, but only found in travelers, immigrants, homosexuals and institutionalized persons. *E. histolytica*-associated dysentery is a common occurrence in the less developed and developing countries of the world, but is more common in areas of low socio-economic status, poor sanitation and nutrition especially in the tropics (Ravdin *et al.*, 2005). Thus the majority of *E. histolytica* infections, morbidity and mortality occur in Africa, Central and South America and the Indian Sub-continent (Haque *et al.*, 2006). However, the rate varies geographically, For instance, 39% was recorded in Bangladesh, 21% in Vietnam and 33% in Columbia (Blessmann and Le van Tannieth, 2006).

Studies in parts of Africa reported prevalence rates of 22% and 21% in South Africa and Egypt respectively (Stauffer *et al.*, 2006). In Nigeria, prevalence rates of 22.3% in Calabar (Meremiku *et al.*, 1997), 21.6% in Enugu (Ozumba, 1997) and 13.7% in Ilesa have been reported (Ogunlesi *et al.*, 2005).

In Kaduna metropolis however, such records do not exist. In addition sewage disposal is mainly by pit latrines and water cistern methods. Indiscriminate disposal of human waste in the poorly developed outskirts where farming is also done as well as inconsistent supply of pipe borne water have resulted in the use of other sources of water which are exposed to faecal contamination.

There is a need to use a rapid method such as the ELISA antigen detection technique instead of the conventional microscopy which may not detect all positive cases. It is therefore our aim to use microscopy and ELISA antibody detection technique to determine the prevalence of *Entamoeba histolytica* infections in patients presenting at government hospitals in Kaduna. The appropriate health authorities would therefore, need baseline data to enable them take decisions with regards to diagnosis of *E. histolytica* infection.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ethical Consideration

Informed consent was obtained from each of the patient or their parents. The work was also approved by the Ethical Committee of the government hospitals used in this study.

Enrolment of patients

All patients presenting to the selected government hospitals in Kaduna with acute and persistent diarrhoea or dysentery within the 18 month period of study were enlisted having consented to participate and fulfilled the inclusion criteria which included acute or persistent diarrhoea and dysenteric syndrome.

Patients with diarrhoea or dysentery on antimicrobial agents were excluded.

Patients visiting the hospital for reasons other than diarrhoea and had no diarrhoeal illness within the last 2 weeks were used as control.

Specimen collection and processing

Three hundred and seventy eight samples (378) comprising 189 stool and 189 blood specimens were aseptically collected from dysentery patients presenting at Barau Dikko, Gwamna Awan and Yusuf Dantsoho general hospitals in Kaduna metropolis.

Formol- Ether Concentration Method

The stool samples were analysed using the Formol-Ether concentration method of Cheesbrough (2005). The emulsified faecal samples were filtered in a two-layered gauze and the filtrate transferred to a conical centrifuge tube containing equal volume of ether and centrifuged for 1 minute at 3,000rpm. After discarding the faecal debris and ether, the sediment was transferred to a clean glass slide and a drop of iodine was added. The entire preparation covered with a cover slip and examined microscopically under x40 objective to identify the trophozoites.

ELISA Antibody Detection Technique

The sera from the blood samples were analysed using the Enzyme Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA) made by TechLab (USA). The first well of the microplate was left blank (control) while 100ul of negative and positive controls were added to the second and third wells respectively. Two drops of the diluted test samples were added to the remaining wells and incubated at room temperature (15-20°C) for 10 min. The contents were then shaken and washed 3 times with diluted buffer. After washing, 2 drops of enzyme conjugate were added to each well and again incubated at room temperature for 5 minutes.

This was followed by another shaking and washing again with buffer after which 2 drops of chromagen was added to each well and again incubated at room temperature. Finally, 2 drops of the stop solution were added to each well and mixed by tapping the strip holder. The results were read with a ELISA machine set for biochromatic readings at 450/650-620nm. The prevalence of *E. histolytica* was determined by the percentage of patients who tested positive for microscopy and ELISA, while the Chi-square was used to determine the association of between *E. histolytica* and the selected variables. All statistical analyses were carried out using the SPSS statistical software.

RESULTS

Of the 189 dysentery patients sampled, 27 (14.3%) were positive for *E. histolytica*, 13 (6.9%) *E. coli* and 4 (2.1%) *G. lamblia* respectively (Table 1). The results in Table 2 below show that *E. histolytica* was statistically associated with age ($p=0.05$), but was not associated with gender and season ($p>0.05$). However, males were more infected (14.6%) than females (14.0%). The rate of infection decreased with age except for age 41 and above (18.2%). The infection rate was higher in the rainy season (15.5%) than dry season (12.9%). *E. histolytica* infection was not

statistically associated with the educational status and type of toilet facility used ($p>0.05$) Table 3. However the results in Table 4 show that the infection was associated with the occupational status and source of drinking water of the patients ($p<0.05$).

Table 1. Prevalence of pathogenic protozoa among diarrhoeic patients

Organism	Number Examined	Number infected	Prevalence (%)
<i>E.histolytica</i>	189	27	14.3
<i>Ent. coli</i>	189	13	6.8
<i>G.lamblia</i>	189	4	2.1

Table 2: Prevalence of *E. histolytica* infection based on gender, age and season.

PARAMETER		NE	No and % positive			X ²	df	p-value
			M	E	ME			
Gender	Male	89	18(20.2)	66(74.2)	13(14.6)	0.014	1	0.95
	Female	100	22(22.0)	81(81.0)	14(14.0)			
Age group (yrs)	1-10	34	14(41.2)	23(67.6)	10(29.4)	9.494	4	0.05
	11-20	29	7(24.1)	21(72.4)	4(13.8)			
	21-30	61	11(18.0)	46(75.4)	6(9.8)			
	31-40	43	4(9.3)	40(93.0)	3(7.0)			
	41-above	22	4(18.2)	17(73.3)	4(18.2)			
Season	Wet	93	25(26.9)	63(67.7)	14(15.1)	0.88	1	0.766
	Dry	96	15(15.6)	84(87.5)	13(13.5)			

Key: NE = Number Examined, M = Microscopy, E=Enzyme Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA), ME = Microscopy and ELISA.

Table 3: Prevalence of *E. histolytica* infection based on educational status and type of toilet facility.

PARAMETER		NE	No and % positive			X ²	df	p-value
			M	E	ME			
Educational status of subject	Not educated	25	4(16.0)	17(68.0)	2(8.0)	3.318	4	0.506
	Primary	50	15(30.0)	41(82.0)	10(20.0)			
	Secondary	70	15(21.7)	50(14.5)	10(14.5)			
	Tertiary	44	6(13.6)	38(11.4)	5(11.4)			
Toilet Facility	Pit	95	25(26.3)	71(13.7)	13(13.7)	0.056	1	0.812
	Water cistern	94	15(16.0)	76(14.9)	14(14.9)			

Key: NE = Number Examined, M = Microscopy, E=Enzyme Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA), ME = Microscopy and ELISA.

Table 4: Prevalence of *E. histolytica* based on occupational status and source of drinking water.

PARAMETER		NE	No and % positive			X ²	d	p.
			M	E	ME		f	value
Occupational Status of subject	Artisan	14	0(0.0)	8(57.1)	0(0.0)	12.153	5	0.033
	Student	59	22(37.3)	45(76.3)	15(25.4)			
	unemployed	31	6(19.4)	24(77.4)	4(12.9)			
	Farmer	8	2(25.0)	8(10.0)	2(25.00)			
	Business	38	5(13.2)	30(78.9)	2(5.3)			
	Civil servant	39	5(12.8)	32(82.1)	4(10.3)			
Source of drinking water	Well	81	24(29.6)	65(80.2)	17(20.9)	0.05	1	0.023
	Tap	108	16	82	10			

Key: NE = Number Examined, M = Microscopy, E=Enzyme Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA)
ME = Microscopy and ELISA.

DISCUSSION

Diarrhoea and Dysentery remain major problems in the developing countries due mainly to poverty, characterized by the absence of potable drinking water, proper sanitary habits, absence of good faecal disposal system, poor hygienic practices by the impoverished citizens and overcrowding (World Health Organization. 1998). Intestinal Amoebiasis due to the infection of *E. histolytica* is ranked third on the list of parasitic protozoan infection leading to death behind malaria and Schistosomiasis (Farthing *et al.*, 1996).

The findings of this study revealed that *E. histolytica* had a prevalence of 14.3% in Kaduna metropolis. This was slightly higher than the 10% cited by WHO, (1995) in the developing world. It was also higher than the 6.3% reported in Calabar (Meremiku *et al.*, 1997) and 0.67% in Ilorin (Fadeyi *et al.*,2009),13.7% in Ilesa (Ogunlesi *et al.*, 2005) but much lower than 21.6% reported in Enugu (Ozumba, 1997). The reason for the disparity was unclear but it could be attributable to differences in study design, patient selection and environmental conditions in the various study centres.

The higher prevalence observed in males (14.6%) than in females (14.0%) agreed with the findings of Erko *et al* (1996), Agi (1997) and Chambers *et al* (1997). The decrease in the infection rate with age agreed with the work of Kobayashi *et al* (1995) and Rai (1997) while the higher prevalence observed in the wet season (15.1%) than dry season (13.5%) agreed with the findings of Ahmed *et al* (1996); Park(2002) and Mawashi (2003).

Subjects using pipe borne water were less infected with *E.histolytica* when compared with people using well water. The association of *E. histolytica* with the source of drinking water of the patients agreed with the findings of Cox (2001), Olsen *et al* (2001), Ogunlesi *et al* (2005) and Rinne *et al* (2005).Most of the wells in the study area were manually dug, uncemented with no casing or covering. Sometimes, the well is contaminated with surface run-off which may be faecally contaminated.

Entamoeba histolytica is often missed in routine stool microscopy as can be seen. The use of single stool specimen per patient for microscopic study may however be contributory to this result. Antigen and Antibody detection tests

are more sensitive than microscopy and results are reproducible as shown by various workers.(Gonin and Trudel,2003) They can also distinguish between the invasive and the non-invasive *E. dispar*. There are several factors responsible for the disparity in the prevalence rate of *Entamoeba histolytica* in any locality. These may include the socio-economic status and population size, expertise of the researchers, the number of subjects enrolled in the study and the duration of the study.

ELISA diagnostic method is a technique which does not require collection of multiple stool specimens per patient and is specific for the diagnosis of *Entamoeba histolytica* infection against microscopy.

Correlation was observed between seropositivity and stool colonization with *E.dispar* and/or *E. histolytica*. Data in this study showed that 77.8% of seropositive individuals as detected by ELISA antibody technique to be colonized with *E. histolytica-E. dispar* complex and 21.8% as detected by microscopy. This is in agreement with the work of Haque *et al* (2000) who found an association between seropositivity and stool colonization with *E. histolytica*. In their study, 52% of the children that were colonized with *E. histolytica* were seropositive and 13% of children whose stools were *E. histolytica* negative were seropositive

Based on the findings of this study; efforts must be made towards the control of *E. histolytica* infection in Kaduna Metropolis. It is recommend that routine screening of dysentery patients for amoebic dysentery should be emphasised as well as the empirical treatment with metronidazole (the anti-parasitic drug recommended by WHO (1995) pending the availability of bacteriological reports.

The poor water supply in the metropolis be improved and additional boiling of water for drinking be emphasized; since some chemical methods of water purification (chlorination) are reportedly ineffective against the cyst of the parasite (Park, 2002).

The general public health enlightenment should be intensified. Poor hand washing practices, for instance, create large pool of carriers of the parasite (Cutting *et al*, 2006).

Other aspects of epidemiology of *E. histolytica* infection like the sanitary conditions of the patients' homes should be studied because such findings would be of great help in reduction and control of the amoebic dysentery.

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